

Forced Migration and Security Threat to Syrian Refugee Woman: A Journey to Latvia

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

People frequently cross international borders in this era of globalization and labor market internationalization. People move for a variety of reasons, such as "money and fortune (job)," "love and family," and "danger and persecution." (Atkinson, [2018](#)). The integration of migrants is a multi-dimensional, two-way procedure that demands work from all parties involved (Aycan, [1997](#)). This includes migrants' ability and willingness to adjust to the host community without having to sacrifice their own culture and identity, and the accompanying willingness on the part of the host government and local institutions to welcome migrants and fulfill the demands of the population. Integration is a continuous and complex process with separate but connected legal, economic, social, and cultural components (Huizinga, [2016](#)).

The context of forced migration includes a variety of topics, including economics, sociology, and humanitarian studies (Barends, [2017](#)). Thus, it has been vital for researchers to comprehend the complex interactions between all of these factors while attempting to comprehend the problem of forced migration. Being dislocated as a human being from one's own country has an effect on a number of aspects of daily life. A displaced individual must contend with challenges in adapting to new surroundings and situations, whether internal or external (Jacobsen and Landau, [2003](#)). Unfortunately, this displaced person frequently has to admit the reality that adapting to a new environment takes time. The process of adaptation can often be delayed when people, such as asylum seekers, are required to move out of their homes frequently before they can be settled permanently (Bernard, [2017](#)).

1.2 Research Question

The primary goal of this study is to identify the major issues that people who are forced to leave their homes must deal with. This study's other objective is to draw attention to the challenges that the Syrian refugee faced as she attempted to integrate into the new society. Therefore, the research question for this study is,

- I. What difficulties did the Syrian refugee experience throughout the period of integration in Latvia?

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Refugees' Integration

In integrating refugees, there are frequently poor standards and a lack of uniformity throughout the EU (Bohrer et. Al., [2019](#)). In addition, despite the requirements established by the EU and international law, the quality of integration strategies for those under international protection varies greatly between European nations. Suitable conditions are an exception rather than the standard, so all of the nations evaluated need to significantly expand their current frameworks for integrating refugees (Bernard, [2017](#)). There are several dimensions of integration including

- 1) Legal integration: access to citizenship, family harmony and reconciliation, and residency.
- 2) Socioeconomic integration: housing, work opportunities, career development, health, and social security
- 3) Sociocultural integration: educational, linguistic, and social orienting and establishing connections (Berry, [1997](#)).

2.2 Elements of Integration

Both internal and external factors have an impact on the word integration. To achieve the desired outcomes of successful integration, the individuals involved in the integration process and those who will be integrated must cooperate (Lancee, [2010](#)). On the other hand, a constant component that can affect integration must be carefully taken into account; the environment in which integration occurs is essential for improved integration outcomes.

Cultural, normative, communicative, and functional integration are the four different types of integration (Montuschi and Cartwright, [2014](#)). To begin with, the idea of cultural integration is developed from several cultural elements that are considered "universals," "specialties," and "alternatives." (Neis and Furukawazono, [2018](#)). Drawing connections between universals and specialties across many cultures will help one better construct an integrated set and understand the differences between these three concepts. On the other hand, The alternatives are the degree

where it appears that other distractions prevent a full integration. As a result, it is recommended that the integration process operate better when alternatives are difficult to identify.

On the other hand, normative integration is assessed in view of how standards and individuals interact. The degree to which the action complies with the intended norms determines the scale of measurement (Montuschi and Cartwright, 2014). In other words, the individual adheres to specific values and norms that are created by a certain community. The individual decides to adhere to these standards in order to fit in with the moral community based on personal convictions. Therefore, when a person follows the set standards, it is more likely that he/she will conduct as anticipated by a particular community.

The language techniques, whether verbal or nonverbal, employed for communication among group members will affect how successfully the integration process goes in terms of communicative integration (Montuschi and Cartwright, 2014). Although the communication network is essential for integration, the intended group's desire to develop their interpersonal skills also plays a critical role. However, irregular communication among some groups frequently manifests as social isolation.

CHAPTER THREE: RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Categories and Sub-categories for the Immigrant's Integration

SL	Categories	Sub-Categories	Participant's statements
01	Motivation ¹	Crisis	<p>a "At that moment, there was a massive war in my country. It was impossible to prevent the war and till now it is unresolved."</p> <p>b "All around us, bombs dropped, and aircraft frequently flew over us."</p>
		Uncertainty	<p>a "I was so scared, and I didn't understand what I should do"</p> <p>b "We prayed before leaving our houses"</p>

¹ Ager, A., & Strang, A. (2008). Understanding integration: A conceptual framework. *Journal of refugee studies*, 21(2), 166-191.

		Security	a “I considered my children's lives. We made an effort to survive. To protect our lives, we fled our houses.”
02	Structural ²	Acquisition of right	a “My son is 11 years old, and my daughter is currently 13. Now, they are going to school.” b “I received government assistance, but it wasn't nearly enough to cover my needs.”
		Access to position	a “I had no job. I did not have money” b “Yes, I have experienced a lot of hardship”
		Status by refugee	a “Well, (pause) when I came here as a refugee, it was quite tough to adjust to the new environment” b “People were certainly afraid at first, but they did not show it to me.”
03	Social ³	Acceptance	a “I believe Latvia is a small country, and they have not welcomed many immigrants from outside of Europe.” b “Honestly speaking, I believe they are not yet prepared to receive immigrants from outside of their territory.”
		Adjustment	a “It was quite tough to adjust to the new environment” b “But the extreme weather here initially bothered me.” c “You are aware that everything requires time to stabilize. The locals also take the time to get to know you.”

² <https://migration.ucdavis.edu/rs/more.php?id=55>

³ Berry, J. W. (2001). A psychology of immigration. *Journal of social issues*, 57(3), 615-631.

			d “Last but not least, the temperature is lower than I had expected.”
		Religious values	a “Since there is a Muslim minority here, my religious functions cannot be celebrated.” b “The basic values and morals here are completely different from those in my home country's religion.” c “It initially gave me discomfort”
		Language	a “The worst part was that I didn't speak Latvian. I was unable to say what I wanted to. Therefore, communication was a major problem at the time” b “Now The problems are easier to manage because I can speak Latvian” c “Certainly, being able to speak Latvian would be incredibly helpful for finding jobs and interacting with others.”
04	Economic ⁴	Labor market access	a “The combination of the language barrier and the difficulty of finding work for an outsider has made my situation more difficult than I had anticipated” b “My neighbours helped me to get a new job”
		Housing	a “Me and my children were living a small room, apartments are expensive here”
		Health services	a “Additionally, so that customers can receive better services, they could hire personnel or staff members who speak English at emergency services like hospitals.”

⁴ Ager, A., & Strang, A. (2008). Understanding integration: A conceptual framework. *Journal of refugee studies*, 21(2), 166-191.

		Standard of living	<p>a “Overall, I think Latvia is more expensive than my home country.”</p> <p>b “The standard of living is higher when compared to the unexpectedly low pay scale.”</p>
05	Cultural ⁵	Assimilation	<p>a “I believe I have already accepted many of the issues (laughing).”</p> <p>b “My uncle who helped me to adapt to the new environment and cultural shock in Latvia.</p>
		Shifting Behavior	<p>a “Then after a few months, I could establish a good relationship with my neighbors.”</p> <p>b “But it took time to melt the ice (laughing)”</p>
		Cohesion	<p>a “At first, I was shocked to see the locals, they were cold, but now I have many local friends here (laughing), and they are assisting me with a lot of things, which I always appreciate.”</p> <p>b “However, people are kind here. They are so much helpful to those in need.”</p>
06	Identification ⁶	Feeling of belonging	<p>a “I found Latvia neat and clean. I really like Riga, it is a small but beautiful city”</p> <p>b “home is always home and nothing can compare with the home country.</p> <p>c “I want to return home and see my other family members and relatives there if my country gets better and the instability is put a stop to.</p> <p>d “Ofcourse, living in my own country is preferable”</p>

⁵ Berry, J. W. (2001). A psychology of immigration. *Journal of social issues*, 57(3), 615-631.

⁶ <https://migration.ucdavis.edu/rs/more.php?id=55>

		Identity in relation	a “But you have to understand we have different cultures and religious values. So it is obvious to have some disparities in terms of beliefs and behaviors.”
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3.2 Discussion

The findings on integration for a Syrian refugee in the host country mentioned several dimensions of adjustment to the host culture and environment. Besides the findings of the study, cross-cultural contact needs several dimensions of adjustment (Searle and Ward [1990](#); Ward and Searle [1991](#); Ward and Kennedy [1992](#)). Furthermore, Along with economic integration, Van Tubergen ([2006](#)) discusses social integration. However, he doesn't specifically discuss refugees; rather, he focuses on immigration in general. Additionally, a "feeling of belonging" and "accepting, understanding, and respecting the local culture" all strongly suggest a psychological adjustment. (Aycan [1997](#)).

However, this study demonstrates the integration of several viewpoints. Additionally, integration involves giving an immigrant an appropriate sense of belonging so that they can feel like a contributing member of society in addition to helping them adjust to life in their new country. While social, economic, and cultural integration is the dominant factors, this research categorizes integration into six dimensions. In the meantime, structure, and identity may not focus strongly all the time but they play a vital role in successful integration. According to the findings, Uncertainty and the immediate war crises served as the driving forces behind integration. Even though the host nation is in Europe, everything was difficult for an immigrant refugee outside of their native country.

Firstly, the weather and environment could be a challenge for an immigrant. The refugee came to Europe from Asia, and she was surprised to find herself in pretty severe weather. Not only was the weather extreme, but the locals initially did not welcome the refugee. Secondly, being unable to find work due to a language barrier, living in a small room with a large family, receiving little government aid, and being unable to access medical care due to a language barrier were the further challenges for her as a refugee immigrant in the host society. Thirdly, Different religious and cultural values ultimately made things worse for the refugee since she

couldn't feel a connection to society, which is unquestionably a weakness of integration and a barrier for an immigrant who can't identify herself as a part of the community.

On the other hand, there are some positive points that the research revealed in the findings, including the fact that locals became more hospitable and friendly towards the refugee after a few days, and they assisted her in finding employment. This allowed the immigrant woman to establish good relationships with the host community. Thus, integration is a process that requires adjustment on the part of the local community as well as the immigrants. Respect and understanding between the two groups are essential for successful integration.

CHAPTER FOUR: CONCLUSION

4.1 Role of social worker to help migrants

Social workers require the skills which are needed to manage the particular difficulties of refugees/immigrants. Social workers are often in charge of ensuring that refugees have access to the necessities of life, such as food, water, shelter, etc. However, Social workers play a significant role in immigrant and refugee groups by reporting problems like employer exploitation, family abuse, sexual offenses, and child abuse to social service and law enforcement organizations, in addition to seeing to it that the physical needs of refugees are addressed. They serve as mediators for individuals who are reluctant to report offenses because they worry about being deported. Last but not least, social workers can act as advocates for immigrants who are the targets of discriminatory legislation and rules.

Difficult to hear from the migrant and me as a social worker

As an immigrant refugee, she found it challenging to both physically and mentally live in the host society as an immigration refugee. She was unable to find employment due to the language barrier, and she and her children were struggling to make ends meet. She had an unpleasant life because of religious and economic disparities. It was difficult for me to hear her when she said she would like to return to her native country when the conflict is immediately stopped because it showed how desperate she is to do so. The fact that we as social workers are unable to provide for their safety and security in the host community is ultimately our problem.

Knowledge contribution (helpful for you as a social worker)

Knowing how important the sense of belonging may be for a refugee to stay in the host country was to me as a social worker. The awareness that we frequently overlook psychological well-being in favor of social and economic well-being was beneficial to me.

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Annex 1

Interview Transcription

Background

Primarily, who is the migrant? The United Nations states, an individual or group of people moving across territorial and political borders to live temporarily or permanently in a location other than their own is referred to as a migrant⁷. A person who leaves their place of origin voluntarily and for personal matters and sets out to reside at a certain location is referred to as a migrant or migrating person. According to the United Nations, in order to be considered a migrant, a person must statistically reside where they moved for a full year (12 months).⁸

Consent of the interview

⁷ Craveiro, D., De Oliveira, I. T., Gomes, M. S., Malheiros, J., Moreira, M. J. G., & Peixoto, J. (2019). Back to replacement migration. *Demographic research*, 40, 1323-1344.

⁸ Bilsborrow, R. E. (1992). Preliminary report of the United Nations Expert Group Meeting on the feminization of internal migration. *International Migration Review*, 26(1), 138-161.

This interview was conducted for the *Youth Intercultural Communication* course. The following interview was conducted in English. Some words or sentences may not accurately convey all the complexities of what was originally spoken due to difficulties with transcription. There is a possibility that the ambiguity and subjectivity of the interview may have slightly changed the original intent of what is being said. For ethical reasons, the respondent's name wouldn't be mentioned in the transcription in order to protect their anonymity. It was said at the time of the interview that “ The Interviewee has the right to silence any question”

Profile of the interviewee

She is a 37-year-old Syrian woman whom I interviewed. Since 2015, she has been residing in Riga, Latvia. Along with her children, she resides there. She has a son and a daughter. She currently works in a grocery shop.

Context of the interview

The Zoom platform was used to conduct the interview. It lasted roughly 31 minutes. On October 31, 2022, in the evening (from 19:00- 19: 31), the interviewer conducted the interview from Ruzomberok, Slovakia, and the interviewee joined the interview from Riga, Latvia. The consent to participate in the interview was read out by the interviewer.

Transcription

1. What was the purpose to come to Latvia?

I left Aleppo almost seven years ago. At that moment, there was a massive war in my country. It was impossible to prevent the war and till now it is unresolved. I was so scared and I didn't understand what should I do. The bomber aircraft was in the air. But after that, I considered my children's lives. We made an effort to survive. To protect our lives, we fled our houses. We couldn't return to the things we left behind when we fled our homes. All around us, bombs dropped, and aircraft frequently flew over us. We prayed before leaving our houses. We were unable to go back.

2. How long time it took for you to plan for the travel?

Due to Azez's location, which is close to the Turkish border, we first traveled there from Aleppo. Azez was also a safer place for us to be compared to the other Syrian cities. There, we stayed for five days. But five days later, we arrived in Turkey. Nevertheless, I had nothing to do and no relatives in Turkey. My family and I remained there for around three months. However, we really wanted to travel to Latvia because I had an uncle over there. Sadly, at that time, the EU forbade Syrian migrants from entering their territory. But after three months, we were able to take my kids to Latvia. It was an extremely difficult situation to migrate to Latvia from Syria.

3. Whom did you migrate with?

You know (pause), My husband was killed in the war and I lost him. With my two kids, I moved to Latvia. My son is 11 years old, and my daughter is currently 13. Now, they are going to school.

4. What kind of difficulties do you face in terms of social, economic, and cultural disparities in Latvia?

Well, (pause) when I came here as a refugee, it was quite tough to adjust to the new environment. Yes, I have experienced a lot of hardship. The worst part was that I didn't speak Latvian. I was unable to say what I wanted to. Therefore, communication was a major problem at the time. I had no job. I did not have money. I received government assistance, but it wasn't nearly enough to cover my needs. People were certainly afraid at first, but they did not show it to me. Since there is a Muslim minority here, my religious functions cannot be celebrated. The basic values and morals here are completely different from those in my home country's religion. Thus, it initially gave me discomfort. Now The problems are easier to manage because I can speak Latvian and I believe I have already accepted many of the issues (laughing). Overall, I think Latvia is more expensive than my home country.

5. Who helped you to overcome any inconvenience resulting from (social, economic, and cultural) as well as cultural shock and adapt to Latvia?

Initially, it was my uncle who helped me to adapt to the new environment and cultural shock in Latvia. Then after a few months, I could establish a good relationship with my neighbors. And they helped me to get a new job. But it took time to melt the ice (laughing)

6. What could help you and other people who are traveling to a new country?

I believe Latvia is a small country, and they have not welcomed many immigrants from outside of Europe. Honestly speaking, I believe they are not yet prepared to receive immigrants from outside of their territory. To help the new people who want to travel, the host communities' level of acceptance should be raised. Additionally, so that customers can receive better services, they could hire personnel or staff members who speak English at emergency services like hospitals.

7. What was your first impression from the country?

I have always been fascinated by Europe. I had never before traveled to Europe. I found Latvia neat and clean. I really like Riga, it is a small but beautiful city. But the extreme weather here initially bothered me. At first, I was shocked to see the locals, they were cold, but now I have many local friends here (laughing), and they are assisting me with a lot of things, which I always appreciate.

8. What about the community in the new country?

I have had a positive experience overall. You are aware that everything requires time to stabilize. The locals also take the time to get to know you. Both good and bad people can be found everywhere. However, people are kind here. They are so much helpful to those in need. (pause) But you have to understand we have different cultures and religious values. So it is obvious to have some disparities in terms of beliefs and behaviors.

9. How do your expectations of the country fit into reality?

I would like to think that it is equally balanced. Riga is actually much more beautiful than was imagined. In this instance, the standard of living is higher when compared to the unexpectedly low pay scale. The combination of the language barrier and the difficulty of finding work for

an outsider has made my situation more difficult than I had anticipated. Last but not least, the temperature is lower than I had expected.

10. Which similarities did you find between your home country and this country?

(pause) It is difficult to say about the similarities because the two countries are totally different. But I can say in my country people love to help a person who needs help. Here in Latvia, if you could build trust with the locals they would help you too for sure but you have to give them some time for that.

11. What would you like to suggest other when traveling in this country?

Well, I have two recommendations for newcomers. First of all, it would be preferable if you already have friends or family members residing in this area so that you could get their help. Certainly, being able to speak Latvian would be incredibly helpful for finding jobs and interacting with others.

12. Could you think about the future to live here in this country?

(pause) well, home is always home and nothing can compare with the home country. I want to return home and see my other family members and relatives there if my country gets better and the instability is put a stop to. Of sure, living in your own country is preferable. It's my house. But my state has to get better to return, the country needs to improve. improve.

Now, I am going to finish the interview. I would like to thank you for your precious time and cooperation.